

Absorbance readings were taken with a Unicam SP-600 spectrophotometer. For pH measurement a Metrohm E-350 pH-meter was used.

Procedure: To a suitable aliquot of Ru^{III} solutions (containing 6 to 45 µg metal) sufficient excess of 6-ANP and pyridine solutions and 4.0 ml of acetate buffer were added and the pH adjusted around 3.0. The solution was heated on a steam bath for ~40 min to ensure full colour development. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and diluted to 10 ml. The absorbance was measured at 530 nm against a reagent blank. The ruthenium concentration was calculated by comparing the absorbance with a calibrated curves.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the solutions containing a fixed amount of Ru^{III} and different concentrations of 6-ANP and pyridine were recorded against reagent blank under various conditions. The reaction was slow at room temperature but when solutions were heated on a steam bath for 30 min the full colour developed. Further heating did not change the absorbances. Therefore, a development time of 40 min was adopted for further studies. The characteristics of the complex studied are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF Ru^{III} TERNARY COMPLEX

Characteristic	Ru ^{III} -complex
Colour	Red-max
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	530
$\epsilon_{\max}$ (l mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	1.2×10^4
pH range for maximum absorbance	1.0–3.5
Reagents needed for full colour development	25 fold 6-ANP and 15 fold pyridine
Molar composition (metal-6-ANP)	1 : 2
Beer's law range (µg ml ⁻¹)	upto 5.5
Optimum range for determination (µg ml ⁻¹)	0.6–4.5
Standard deviation calculated from 10 determinations	0.002

The molar absorptivity of the ternary complex of the metal has been found to be more than its complex only with 6-ANP² (22500 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The ternary complex seems to have been stabilised by mixed ligation with pyridine.

Effect of diverse ions: In determination of 2 ppm of Ru^{III} the following ions were tolerated: Cl⁻, Br⁻, CH₃COO⁻ (5000); F⁻, NO₂⁻ (1000); oxalate, I⁻ (500); Cd^{II}, PO₄³⁻, citrate (200); SCN⁻ (100). Thiourea, NO₃⁻, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} interfere.

References

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Potassium *N*-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate as a Gravimetric Reagent for Thorium(IV)

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ALTHOUGH several reagents have been recommended for gravimetric determination of thorium, only a few are in the actual use¹. Thorium is generally estimated as ThO₂ through ignition of precipitates formed with ammonium hydroxide or oxalic acid. Prior removal of interfering elements is essential in all the cases. Although several other carboxylic acids and certain amines are also used for precipitation², the present report is the first instance of using a Schiff base as gravimetric reagent for thorium. The title reagent is found versatile in forming well-defined metal chelates with a variety of metal ions³. Its reaction with Th^{IV} is quantitative, and since the metal chelate formed is also insoluble in aqueous media, it is well-suited for determining thorium gravimetrically.

Experimental

Potassium *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate (KH Nap : gly) was prepared as follows. Potassium hydroxide (0.56 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in hot methanol (30 ml), and after adding glycine (0.75 g, 0.01 mol), the mixture was stirred magnetically. When the mixture became homogeneous, a solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1.72 g, 0.01 mol) in hot methanol (20 ml) was added to it. A yellow precipitate which separated out immediately, was filtered hot, washed three times with 10 ml portions of methanol, sucked dry, and then crystallised from hot methanol as yellow crystals (80%), m.p. 250°. The compound was characterised on the basis of its micro-analytical, and uv, ir and nmr spectral data³.

A freshly prepared 2% aqueous ethanolic (90% v/v) solution of the reagent was used for precipitating thorium. A stock solution of Th(NO₃)₄·5H₂O of known concentration (~5.5 g per dm³ of aqueous solution) was prepared and used. Parallel determinations of thorium using oxalic acid⁴ were also carried out for comparison.

Typical procedure for determining thorium using the Schiff base reagent was as follows. An aliquot (~25 ml) of stock solution was diluted to ~100 ml, and its pH adjusted to 4.0. To this solution, stirred and heated to ~80°, was added the reagent solution (~25 ml) till the formation of yellow precipitate ceased. Then 1 ml more of the reagent was added, and after heating on a water-bath for 5 min, the precipitated complex was collected on a Whatman no. 41 filter and washed with water containing 1% ethanol. The precipitate-

after incineration in a previously weighed platinum crucible, was ignited to ThO_2 at 600-700°, and the thorium content determined from the weight of ThO_2 left.

Results and Discussion

Thorium, alone and in presence of interfering metals, was determined several times using the new reagent. Encouraged by the excellent accuracy and precision of the results obtained (Table 1), further investigation was undertaken. It was found that even ten times excess of chloride, nitrate, sulphate and acetate are tolerated in these determinations. Comparative evaluation of the performance of the new reagent, with that of oxalic acid, revealed that the two methods are almost equally effective in determining thorium (Table 1). However, unlike the oxalic acid method in which the precipitate needs long settling time, the product obtained with the new reagent is ready for filtration minutes after its precipitation. The resulting rapidity of determination thus renders the new reagent preferable to oxalic acid, the most commonly used reagent for the purpose. Since the best analytical results for thorium are obtained gravimetrically¹, the expeditiousness of the new method holds considerable promise.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THORIUM*

Sl. no.	Weight of ThO_2 based on thorium content of sample used g	Weight of ThO_2 , g		Error, %	
		Using oxalic Acid (A)	Using KH Nap : gly (B)	(A)	(B)
1	0.0508	0.0510	0.0508	0.39	0.00
2	0.0636	0.0638	0.0638	0.31	0.31
3	0.0762	0.0766	0.0764	0.52	0.26
4	0.0478	0.0478	0.0476	0.00	0.42
5	0.0598	0.0596	0.0596	0.33	0.33
6	0.0718	0.0716	0.0718	0.28	0.00
7	—	0.0770	0.0768	—	—
8	—	0.0960	0.0962	—	—

$\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ used in Sl. nos. 1 to 3. A synthetic mixture, approximating monazite in composition, used in nos. 4 to 6, and a sample of Travancore monazite used in nos. 7 and 8. Interfering ions (Sl. nos. 4 to 8) eliminated by usual methods, before precipitating thorium.

Elemental analysis of the complex formed with the new reagent is in agreement with 1 : 2 thorium-ligand stoichiometry. The complex is a non-electrolyte, since it is non-conducting in DMF. Infrared spectral data revealed that the reagent is a dibasic tridentate ONO donor³, and that the complex is representable as $[\text{Th}(\text{Nap : gly})_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Thermogravimetric analysis clearly indicated that a molecule of water is lost quantitatively from the complex in the temperature range 95-105°. Decomposition of the remainder of the complex is slow, but is complete at 600° leaving behind ThO_2 .

Composition of the complex precipitated in different experiments varied slightly, evidently because in the case of thorium^{1,2,5} coordination by

OH is not precluded fully even at pH 4. Hence, as in the other methods², direct weighing of the precipitate is not recommended.

References

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Trace Determination of Arsenic and Cobalt by Differential Pulse Polarography

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A precise, accurate and sensitive technique developed for trace determination of arsenic and cobalt gains importance as the former is a poison and also a potential carcinogen¹, while the latter is involved in numerous enzymatic reactions. References of their analysis by a wide variety of techniques, like atomic absorption spectroscopy^{2,3}, gas chromatography^{4,5}, polarography^{6,7} and inverse voltammetry^{8,9} are found in literature. A highly sensitive and particularly reliable analytical procedure for precise determination of arsenic and cobalt by differential pulse polarography is reported in the present communication.

Experimental

Cobaltous sulphate (A.R., S.M.) and sodium arsenite (Riedel) were used in the preparation of 0.1M stock solutions of Co^{II} and As^{III} in water. Triple-distilled water was used throughout the studies. 1% stock solutions of bromophenol blue (BPB) and Triton-X-100 were prepared in water and used after suitable dilutions to 0.01% working solutions. A 0.1% solution of gelatin was prepared afresh each day owing to its unstable nature. All other normal precautions of trace analysis were taken throughout the work.

Polarograms were recorded on a Metrom-E-506 Polarecord with E-505 series-03 polarography stand. A three-electrode system of DME as indicator electrode and two Ag/AgCl electrodes as